

THE EFFECTS OF NEGOTIATION BEHAVIOR ON THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS OF DISTRIBUTORS WHILE PROVIDING THE PREFERRED CUSTOMER STATUS TO THE WHOLESALER IN BATANGAS

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative research aims to understand the impact of negotiation behavior on distributors' decision-making process when granting preferred customer status to wholesalers. The study will involve interviews with 10 wholesalers and 10 distributors using semi-structured questionnaires. The distributors will be the unit of analysis, and the study will measure the effects of negotiation behavior on the decision-making process using a 3-decision-making process. The research will identify different negotiation behaviors used by wholesalers, such as competitive and integrative, and recommend strategies to improve their chances of obtaining preferred customer status. The findings show that integrative activities have a favorable impact on outcomes, while competing behaviors have no influence. Distributors value effective communication, account expertise, and punctuality, while preferred customer status is based on character and loyalty. Wholesalers value professionalism, honesty, partnership, and ethical procedures to achieve favored status. Both parties emphasize the importance of developing relationships, mutual satisfaction, ethical behavior, and integrative negotiation behaviors for effective negotiations.

Keywords: *Preferred customer status, negotiation behaviors, wholesalers, distributors*

INTRODUCTION

Negotiation processes between distributor and wholesaler businesses are critical for business relationships. According to David S. Bauders, CEO of SPARXiQ, negotiating dynamics have a considerable impact on distributor earnings, with skilled negotiation methods leading to big margin improvements. Bauders emphasizes the necessity of negotiation training for sellers, citing a considerable skill gap between buyers and sellers in the wholesale distribution market (Bauders, 2023).

Saorin-Iborra and Cubillo (2018) suggest that a distributor company's negotiation strategy can affect the wholesale company's satisfaction, which in turn affects the relationship quality and long-term profit maximization. This study uses the negotiation behavior continuum to analyze distributor decision-making processes, focusing on the distributor as the unit of analysis.

Furthermore, Bauders (2023) emphasizes the negative consequences of accepting poor compensation without using good bargaining methods. In a competitive climate where buyers are skilled negotiators, distributors must develop advanced negotiating skills in order to get fair terms that represent the value they provide to their buyers.

Boothby et al. (2023) note the potential of negotiation research to provide useful insights for enhancing decision-making in real-world social interactions. Researchers can assist distributors and wholesalers in improving profitability in the wholesale distribution industry by establishing realistic frameworks and tactics for handling negotiation dynamics.

Preferred customer status is crucial in distributor negotiations as it significantly influences the outcome. These customers, who have made multiple transactions or spent a certain amount, often receive special benefits like discounts and early access to new products. Understanding their status can help both parties modify their approach, potentially leading to increased discounts or negotiation on other terms (Fuchs, 2023).

In the context of distributor-wholesaler partnerships, preferred customer status is a strategic designation that distributors give to particular wholesalers. Preferred customer status in distributor-wholesaler relationships refers to a strategic arrangement in which selected clients are granted special rights and rewards based on their purchase history or other qualifying considerations. These "preferred" clients receive preferential treatment, which may include discounts, exclusive product access, or other benefits designed to improve their experience and encourage continuous involvement with the distributor or wholesaler.

Preferred customer status impacts inventory management, allowing businesses to control inventory levels and reduce stockouts. Pricing benefits, such as discounts or preferential terms, are crucial for maintaining wholesale profit margins. These customers can optimize pricing strategies, stay competitive, and protect profitability, thereby enhancing business performance (Surefront, 2023).

Preferred customer status is a key factor in the distribution industry, as it enhances customer satisfaction, loyalty, and business growth. It allows preferred clients to receive personalized support, tailored marketing, and exclusive deals, which can lead to increased sales and revenue. This status also strengthens the inter-organizational ties between wholesalers and distributors, fostering relationship growth and supplier loyalty. (Surefront, 2023).

Obtaining preferred customer status also encourages wholesalers to commit to the relationship and innovate, leading to improved quality and innovation. It also positively impacts distributors' pricing, as they often pay lower costs for goods. Understanding distributor satisfaction is crucial for a company's competitive advantage in the distribution business. (Surefront, 2023)

Negotiation behaviors are essential for improving the competitive environment, but there is a lack of research on these behaviors on the Saorín-Iborra continuum. This study aims to focus on customer negotiation behaviors and their impact on distributors' decision-making processes, aiming to optimize negotiation strategies and enhance competitive advantage.

The distribution industry plays a crucial role in the market supply chain, ensuring efficient movement of goods from manufacturers to end consumers. Effective distribution helps manage inventory levels, minimize carrying costs, and meet customer demand. Understanding negotiation dynamics is crucial for optimizing costs, managing risks, and achieving overall business success. Bemelmans et al. (2015)

In conclusion, understanding negotiation behaviors and granting preferred customer status is essential for optimizing business relationships, building mutually beneficial partnerships, and generating success in the distribution industry.

Research Questions

This study explored the importance of 13 negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process of distributors when granting preferred customer status. It fills a gap in the literature by focusing on the effects of these behaviors on the decision-making process of distributors. Previous studies have only examined customer satisfaction, not negotiation behaviors. The study provides a theoretical contribution by filling a literature gap by examining the importance of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making of the distributors while providing preferred customer status to the wholesaler. Specifically, this paper sought to answer the following:

1. From the point of view of the distributors, what is extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status:
 - a. Good working Relations;
 - b. Working Relationships that convey competitive advantage; and
 - c. Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice?

2. From the point of view of the wholesaler what is the extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status:
 - a. Good working Relations;
 - b. Working Relationships that convey competitive advantage; and
 - c. Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice?
 3. What are the similarities and differences between the distributors' and wholesalers' perceived extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors on the distributor's decision-making process?
 4. What are the negotiation behaviors that the wholesaler can adopt in order to obtain customer-preferred status?
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METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

A descriptive approach was employed in this qualitative study. The descriptive design analysed interviewees' perceptions or experiences related to negotiation behavior that can affect the decision-making process for granting customer-preferred status to the wholesaler. To find the effects of negotiation behaviors, the researcher conducted interviews with the distributors and selected wholesalers (who have customer-preferred status). The semi-structured interview consists of 5 questions specifically focusing on the 13 negotiation behaviors and how each negotiation behavior affects the decision-making process of the distributor in granting preferred customer status. Descriptive studies yield rich data that leads to important recommendations, which is the goal of this study.

This study aimed to provide an understanding of the negotiation process between selected beverage distributors and wholesalers. It is important to note that the findings of this study cannot be generalized to other industries or regions without taking into account their unique characteristics. The data collected in this study is based on the perspective of beverage distributors and wholesalers and may be subject to potential sources of bias. These biases include a common scale used in measuring responses, data collected from a single source, and social desirability responses. Although every effort has been made to mitigate method and response biases in the data collection process, it is impossible to completely eliminate them. The study findings were expected to provide valuable insights into the negotiation behavior in the decision-making process for distributors and wholesalers and could be used to inform future research in this area.

B. Locale of the Study

Batangas, specifically its northern section, was chosen as the study's focus point due to its prominence as a thriving industrial powerhouse in Calabarzon. Batangas stands out

as a dynamic location ideal for exploration, thanks to its thriving economy, which is characterized by the presence of several economic zones and a robust population of micro, small, and medium-sized firms. The province's rapid urbanization, which is evident from its excellent average annual growth rate of 2.13%, emphasizes its significance as a significant economic hub in the Philippines (City Government of Batangas, 2023).

Batangas, with its significant presence of distributors and wholesalers, is an ideal location for analysing negotiating dynamics and preferred client arrangements. The province's thriving beverage industry, accounting for 2.5% of the Philippine GDP according to Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA), it is a key contributor to economic growth. The study focuses on the northern region of Batangas to capitalize on the area's rapid urbanization and economic dynamism, providing a more nuanced understanding of negotiation behaviors and preferred customer dynamics in distributor-wholesaler relationships. This strategic choice aligns with the research aims, allowing a thorough examination of negotiating dynamics in a dynamic corporate context.

C. Respondents of the Study

In this study, respondent selection is crucial for generating valuable insights into negotiating dynamics and desired customer arrangements in Batangas' beverage distribution sector. To gain a thorough understanding of the subject, the researcher conducted interviews with a carefully selected group of respondents, including 10 wholesalers and 10 beverage distributors.

The 10 recognized wholesalers represent a varied cross-section of the sector, with varying sizes, specialties, and business methods. These wholesalers were chosen because they are preferred customers, and they provide distinct insights on the issues that influenced their selection as well as the benefits of their privileged status. The study's in-depth interviews provided vital insights on the criteria utilized by distributors to grant preferred customer status, as well as the impact of this designation on wholesalers' operations and relationships with distributors.

Similarly, the 10 beverage distributors chosen for interviews reflect important stakeholders in the distribution network, particularly those with substantial experience negotiating deals in the beverage industry. These individuals provide executive-level insights on the issues that come with operating in a highly competitive market, including comprehensive evaluations of the internal impediments they confront and the techniques they use to overcome them. By diving into their experiences and perspectives, the study hoped to shed light on the intricacies of awarding preferred customer status to wholesalers, as well as the ramifications for distributor-wholesale relationships.

The study sought to collect a plethora of qualitative data through these interviews, which led to a better understanding of bargaining behaviors, decision-making processes, and the dynamics of preferred customer arrangements in Batangas' beverage distribution sector. By collaborating with experienced individuals from both sides of the distribution network, the study hoped to shed light on the complexities of distributor-wholesaler

relationships and provide ideas for optimizing the preferred customer status program for mutual gain.

D. Sampling Design

The study utilized a purposive sampling strategy. Purposive sampling is a class of non-probability sampling procedures in which units are chosen because they possess traits that are required in the sample. In other words, units are chosen "on purpose" in purposive sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022). This was used to choose participants who might provide important insights into bargaining practices and the awarding of preferred customer status in Batangas' beverage distribution sector.

A sample size of 20 respondents is sufficient due to the study's emphasis on depth over breadth. Due to the study's qualitative nature, in-depth analysis of each respondent's thoughts is possible thanks to a variety of data collection techniques like interviews and observations. By putting the depth and saturation of data ahead of statistical representativeness, the study can effectively unearth subtle insights and achieve its goals within the established scope and limits. The major goal is to get feedback from distributors and wholesalers who are actively participating in negotiation procedures, notably in the beverage distribution niche.

Criteria for selection:

The first criterion for selection includes persons who have been directly involved in negotiating procedures for at least two years, primarily in the beverage distribution sector. This criterion ensures that participants have appropriate expertise and insights into the complexities of negotiation dynamics that exist in the sector.

The second criterion focuses on beverage distributors operating in the Batangas region. These wholesalers negotiate with distributors on a regular basis, making them well-positioned to provide insights into negotiation processes and the dynamics of preferred customer agreements.

RESULTS

The study used qualitative research methods to investigate the extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. Interviews with sales supervisors, proprietors, and personnel were conducted, and their responses were analyzed using IBM SPSS Text Analytics Software. The results provide valuable insights for distributors and wholesalers, helping them understand market trends, consumer preferences, and supply chain dynamics. This information can optimize operations, improve product offerings, and enhance customer satisfaction. The

findings can also help identify new market opportunities, develop effective marketing strategies, and enhance competitive advantage in the industry.

Negotiation in general.

Negotiation success requires equal authority and understanding of different levels of authority within an organization (David, 2006). Sales technique involves positioning a product to reach more customers, using strategies like route planning and pricing. Negotiation focuses on settling disagreements and reaching agreements, focusing on communication skills, account knowledge, timeliness, and relationship-building. Building a positive rapport with potential clients, identifying customer wants, and tailoring products to specific requirements is crucial for successful negotiations.

Preferred Customer Status

Wholesalers with preferred customer status gain more benefits from their distributors, including access to innovations, discounts, and faster supplies. This enhances competitiveness and access to technological innovations, as highlighted by a study by Ellis et al. (2012).

The study explores preferred customer status in the beverage distribution industry, focusing on factors like credibility, character, financial capability, loyalty, and adherence to standards. It highlights the influence of wholesaler behavior on eligibility and the importance of loyalty and support in building preferred customer connections. Benefits include increased credit limits, discounts, and priority delivery.

According to Ellis et al. (2012), a wholesaler can demonstrate its reliability by consistently and predictably fulfilling its commitments. This, in turn, assures distributors that the wholesaler will not let them down and will keep its promises. Furthermore, Huttinger et al. (2012) found that customer loyalty is a crucial factor in determining customer attractiveness. This aligns with the study by Schiele et al. (2015), which suggests that customer attractiveness is a vital component in achieving preferred customer status.

Distributors assess wholesaler desirability based on factors such as character, confidence, purchasing ability, accessible resources, and information sharing. They prioritize payment timeliness and transaction manner, with some prioritizing timely payments and others focusing on convenience and efficiency. Relationship building is crucial for effective wholesaler-distributor partnerships, with wholesalers' attitudes serving as a reference for future deals.

Satisfaction with wholesaler organizations is measured by metrics like order recurrence, continuous commercial interactions, on-time payment, productivity, and meeting supplier needs. Suppliers can upgrade satisfied customers to preferred statuses, while maintaining regular statuses for those who provide adequate satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is dynamic and relative, influenced by emotional responses, perceptions of quality, and equity. Distributors emphasize the importance of developing long-term connections with wholesalers that value mutual pleasure and contribute to

commercial success. Positive negotiation tactics, such as cooperation and understanding, lead to higher satisfaction levels, while bad behavior can reduce satisfaction and strain the relationship. Effective communication and ease of engagement during negotiations promote productive discussions and increase wholesaler satisfaction.

Competitive negotiation behaviors

The study explores the impact of competitive negotiation on the beverage distribution industry, focusing on the importance of honesty, professionalism, and business relationships. Over half of the respondents admitted to intentionally misinterpreting factual information during the negotiation process, highlighting the complex interplay between ethical considerations, professionalism, and business relationships. Misinformation can erode trust and harm relationships with wholesalers in the long run, potentially damaging a distributor's reputation and resulting in a loss of business.

Traditional competitive bargaining is also discussed, with respondents emphasizing the value of gathering competitor information for various goals, but acknowledging the ethical implications of these techniques. Competitive advantage is emphasized, with D-9 highlighting the significance of remaining competitive in terms of price and products, while D-10 emphasizes negotiation capability enhancement. Respondents differ on whether competitive conduct affects the likelihood of receiving preferred customer status, with D-1, D-2, D-4, D-7, and D-8 recognizing the value of competitive conduct in learning about competitors' plans and movements, while D-7 and D-8 emphasize the importance of honesty and integrity in business operations.

Bluffing is a technique used by companies to gain a competitive advantage and seize business opportunities, but it can also be detrimental in negotiations due to concerns about honesty and integrity. The study highlights the importance of ethical negotiation practices in achieving success. Respondents prioritize professionalism and moral conduct in competitive bargaining, avoiding unethical tactics like breaking into opponents' networks. They focus on direct competition, valuing positive relationships with suppliers and trust, and preferring to obtain data through legal means rather than deceptive methods.

Inappropriate information gathering is also discussed, with some respondents using paid colleagues or contacts to gain a competitive advantage and increase revenue by learning about an opponent's viewpoint. Ethical considerations and company policies are also acknowledged, as are resource restrictions and financial limitations as reasons for not using unethical information-gathering strategies.

Integrative negotiation behaviors

Integrative negotiation behavior is a transparent and honest exchange of information and a willingness to work collaboratively towards a mutually beneficial outcome (Saorín-Iborra, 2008). It has been found to be positively related to customer satisfaction, as it creates a cooperative atmosphere that facilitates the creation of trust and commitment between the negotiating parties. Trust is a crucial factor in the development of long-term

relationships between organizations, making integrative negotiation behavior even more valuable as it fosters an environment of trust and cooperation, leading to better business relationships and outcomes.

Active listening is essential for understanding counterparts' needs during discussions and building trust among the parties involved. Maintaining positive relationships with wholesalers is crucial for generating sales and facilitating successful transactions. Trust and loyalty are essential for building credibility and fostering mutually beneficial partnerships. Collaborative partnerships benefit both sides, leading to higher revenue and profitability.

Obtaining positive results in negotiations is crucial for building strong relationships with wholesalers, achieving mutual understanding, and generating sales. Cooperation facilitates the resolution of issues and challenges, allowing for efficient problem-solving and driving business growth. Mutual satisfaction is emphasized as a key factor in driving corporate success, with satisfied wholesalers contributing to a healthy business ecosystem, long-term profitability, and sustainability.

Free flow of information is essential for building trust and relationships among distributors, promoting mutual understanding and agreements. Respondents D-1 and D-5 limit information flow to generate sales, prioritizing strategic use without disclosing unnecessary information. Respondents D-6 and D-9 prioritize mutual gain and trust, while sincerity and transparency in communication techniques are essential.

Minimizing differences in business to increase sales, establish a positive partnership, and achieve common goals aligns with wholesalers' preferred customer status. Trust is also emphasized as a key factor in building positive relationships with distributors, fostering loyalty, and ensuring information reliability.

Inclusive decision-making is crucial for promoting mutual understanding and addressing all issues in discussions. However, there is a divided opinion on whether it influences distributors' willingness to give preferred customer status. Factors like dependability and consistency can also influence the granting of preferred customer status.

Measurable items of the decision-making process

Good working relations

The quality of working relationships with wholesalers is directly linked to the distributor's choice to offer preferred customer status. Stronger ties result in improved sales, mutual satisfaction, and smoother transactions. Research emphasizes the importance of rapport and collaboration in supplier-buyer interactions. Proactive efforts include understanding customer demands, resolving difficulties efficiently, and adapting actions to promote satisfaction. Customer satisfaction motivates efforts to improve relationships and potentially gain preferred customer status.

The study reveals that negotiation behaviors have minimal impact on gaining information about an opponent, seeking mutual satisfaction, and maintaining a productive personal

relationship. Cooperation, open communication, trusting other negotiators, and involving all parties in decision-making are key to positive results. Intentional fabrication and information obtaining through networks have the lowest impact. Perceptions of customer status.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship and Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs Seeking mutual satisfaction has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said that Minimizing differences among the parties, Trusting the position and information of other negotiators, Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Table 1. From the point of view of the distributors, what is extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status:

Negotiation Behaviors	Good working relations		Working relationships that convey competitive advantage.		Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent	1.20	to a very little or no extent	1.20	to a very little or no extent	1.30	not at all
Gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network	1.40	to a very little or no extent	1.40	to a very little or no extent	1.40	not at all
Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Gaining information about a party by paying its contacts	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all

Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs	4.60	to a very great extent.	4.60	to a very great extent	6.40	great
Seeking mutual satisfaction	3.80	to a great extent	3.80	to a great extent	5.20	considerable
Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship	5.00	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent	7.00	very great
Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties	5.00	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent	7.00	very great
Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators	4.80	to a very great extent	4.80	to a very great extent	7.00	very great
Minimizing differences among the parties	4.70	to a very great extent	4.70	to a very great extent	6.60	very great
Trusting the position and information of other negotiators	4.40	to a great extent	4.50	to a very great extent	6.20	great
Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process	4.60	to a very great extent	4.60	to a very great extent	6.50	very great

Legend: (Good working relations and Working relationships that convey competitive advantage). 1-1.4 to a very little or no extent, 1.5-2.4 to a little extent; 2.5-3.4 to some extent, 3.5-4.4 to a great extent, 4.5- to a very great extent. (Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice) 1-1.4 = not at all, 1.5-2.4 = very little, 2.5-3.4 = somewhat, 3.5-4.4 = moderate, 4.5-5.4 = considerable, 5.5-6.4 = great, and 6.4-7 = very great.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent of effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred

customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else, gaining information about a party by paying its contacts and Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship and Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs Seeking mutual satisfaction has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said that Minimizing differences among the parties, Trusting the position and information of other negotiators, Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Working relationships that convey competitive advantage.

The wholesaler-distributor relationship is crucial for distributors to gain preferred customer status. Strong relationships lead to increased sales and effective coordination. Techniques for improving relationships include planning, active listening, training, and marketing strategies. Professionalism is essential. Trust, collaboration, and open communication are key factors for a competitive advantage. Minimizing gaps and trusting negotiators' positions are also important.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else, gaining information about a party by paying its contacts and Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

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when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs and Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said that Minimizing differences among the parties, and Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 70% of the respondents said that Seeking mutual satisfaction, and Trusting the position and information of other negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice

Wholesaler negotiating approach significantly influences distributors' willingness to offer preferred customer status, offering superior treatment and better product quality. Strategies include presenting advantages, analyzing wholesaler needs, providing promotions, ensuring product availability, and following marketing trends. A customer-centric strategy prioritizes addressing wholesaler needs and building trust through personalized communication. Seeking mutual satisfaction, fostering positive interactions, and cooperating effectively are key to establishing a preferred customer status. However, intentional falsification and information acquisition through competitors' networks have negative impacts.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else, gaining information about a party by paying its contacts and Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship and Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs and Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 80% of the respondents said that Minimizing differences among the parties, and Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the

decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 70% of the respondents said that Seeking mutual satisfaction, and Trusting the position and information of other negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Wholesaler point of view

Negotiation in general

Wholesalers emphasize the importance of kindness, respect, and professionalism in their interactions with salespeople and distributors. They use courteous language and express concern for their needs, fostering a positive environment for discussions. They also focus on building positive business relationships by respectfully communicating, understanding product releases, and demonstrating professionalism. They prioritize direct communication with distribution stakeholders while maintaining a respectful tone. They also prioritize volume and capacity in commercial dealings while maintaining a low-profile image. Humility and consideration are also crucial, as wholesalers strive to minimize boastfulness while actively seeking out distribution staff's needs and offering support.

Preferred Customer Status

Wholesalers' attractiveness is influenced by their kindness, respect, and professionalism, which fosters positive business relationships and loyalty. Distributors' satisfaction is influenced by higher discounts, credit limitations, and meeting sales targets. Trust and honesty are crucial for maintaining a stable business climate. Preferred customer status is a classification for wholesalers who receive better deals, discounts, promotions, and incentives from their distributors. This status is determined by volume of orders and includes priority delivery, unique discounts, and customized assistance. Wholesalers with large orders and support for their distributor's business objectives are more likely to be given preferred status.

Competitive negotiation behaviors

The interview highlights the importance of honesty and integrity in negotiations, avoiding misleading tactics to build trust and maintain long-term business partnerships. It also emphasizes the negative effects of misinformation on a wholesaler's reputation and business prospects. Traditional competitive bargaining involves understanding competitors' bargaining stances and techniques, staying current with industry developments, and obtaining information from competitors' networks. Bluffing, while used for sales generation, can destroy trust and credibility. Ethical sales strategies and avoiding misleading tactics are suggested. The text also discusses the potential benefits of manipulating an opponent's network, emphasizing a positive work environment and ethical norms. Respondents strongly support ethical business practices, rejecting unethical practices like paying associates for information about opponents' opinions. They

believe integrity and fairness are crucial in commercial relationships and worry about the negative impact on supplier relationships.

Integrative negotiation behaviors

Active listening is essential in negotiations to understand counterparts' needs, gain critical information, and ensure clear communication. Building positive relationships with distributors is crucial for long-lasting and profitable business relationships, leading to improved prospects and supplier credibility. Collaboration, mutual satisfaction, and transparency are key to achieving preferred customer status. Mutual satisfaction can strengthen supplier relationships, leading to increased promotions and incentives.

Transparency and trust are crucial in negotiations, as they foster productive collaboration and successful business relationships. Open communication and information sharing are strategic values in achieving preferred customer status.

Adapting to distributors' needs and demonstrating a pragmatic approach to bargaining are essential for successful transactions. Trust in distributor information is based on perceived value and control over inventory. Respecting contractual agreements and information provided by distributors is critical for establishing a positive connection and influencing the likelihood of attaining preferred status.

Involving all parties in decision-making processes ensures diverse viewpoints and considers ideas, benefiting collaboration and creativity. However, caution is needed in evaluating information sources during negotiations.

Measurable items of the decision-making process

Good working relations. The study found that negotiation behaviors significantly influence positive working relationships. High scores were given to understanding counterparts' demands, seeking mutual satisfaction, maintaining healthy relationships, collaborating, and ensuring information flow. Trusting other negotiators' stances and knowledge was also highly rated. Involving parties in decision-making was also highly rated. However, unethical behavior, bluffing, and influencing others were deemed low. The study also found that payment for knowledge had a low score, indicating its no impact on relationships.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent, gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network, Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else gaining information about a party by paying its contacts has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Table 2. From the point of view of the wholesaler what is the extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status:

Negotiation Behaviors	Good working relations		Working relationships that convey competitive advantage.		Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Gaining information about a party by paying its contacts	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	not at all
Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs	4.90	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent.	6.90	very great
Seeking mutual satisfaction	4.90	to a very great extent.	4.90	to a very great extent.	5.20	considerable
Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship	5.00	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent.	6.90	very great
Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties	4.90	to a very great extent.	4.90	to a very great extent.	7.00	very great
Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators	4.90	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent.	6.90	very great

Minimizing differences among the parties	5.00	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent.	6.80	very great
Trusting the position and information of other negotiators	4.90	to a very great extent.	4.90	to a very great extent.	6.90	very great
Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process	4.40	to a great extent	4.50	to a very great extent.	6.10	great

Legend: (Good working relations and Working relationships that convey competitive advantage). 1-1.4 to a very little or no extent, 1.5-2.4 to a little extent; 2.5-3.4 to some extent, 3.5-4.4 to a great extent, 4.5- to a very great extent.(Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice) 1-1.4 = not at all, 1.5-2.4 = very little, 2.5-3.4 = somewhat, 3.5-4.4 = moderate, 4.5-5.4 = considerable, 5.5-6.4 = great, and 6.4-7 = very great.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship and Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs and Seeking mutual satisfaction, Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties and Trusting the position and information of other negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 60% of the respondents said that Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Working relationships that convey competitive advantage. The result emphasizes the importance of kindness, support, collaboration, adaptability, and trustworthiness in relationships between wholesalers and distributors. It highlights the need for mutual growth, effective marketing techniques, and fostering a positive working environment. Negotiation behaviors, such as understanding counterpart demands, maintaining healthy relationships, and ensuring information flow, significantly influence competitive advantages.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent, gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network, Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else gaining information about a party by

paying its contacts has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs, Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship, Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators and Minimizing differences among the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Seeking mutual satisfaction, Trusting the position and information of other negotiators and Seeking mutual satisfaction, Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties and Trusting the position and information of other negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 70% of the respondents said that Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice. The text emphasizes the importance of treating distributors with respect and building positive relationships, as well as adapting to their preferences and adopting a customer-centric approach. It also highlights the need for sales volume and performance to achieve preferred customer status. Factors such as open communication, trust in other negotiators, and inclusive decision-making procedures contribute to a wholesaler's perception of being a preferred client. Factors like being aware of counterparts' demands, seeking mutual satisfaction, maintaining healthy personal relationships, and ensuring a free flow of information significantly impact positive working relationships.

Majority of the respondents said the competitive behavior has no extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent, gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network, Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else gaining information about a party by paying its contacts has no extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Majority of the respondents said the integrative behavior has a great extent on the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 100% of the respondents said that Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties has a very great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status. 90% of the respondents said that Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs, Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship, Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators.

Minimizing differences among the parties and Trusting the position and information of other negotiators has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-

making process when granting preferred customer status. 60% of the respondents said that Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process has great extent of the effect of negotiation behaviors in the decision-making process when granting preferred customer status.

Distributors View

Batangas distributors prioritize communication skills, account knowledge, timeliness, and relationship-building strategies in customer negotiations. They value preferred customer status based on factors like character, payment regularity, and loyalty. Some use deception tactics, such as bluffing and manipulation, to increase sales, raising ethical concerns. Active listening and understanding demands are critical for establishing trust and strengthening corporate partnerships. Inclusive decision-making methods are appreciated for considering multiple perspectives and generating mutually beneficial outcomes. Minimizing disagreements and establishing trust are essential components of effective negotiations. Respondents ranked cooperation, open communication, and trusting the stance of other negotiators as bad. They supported participation in decision-making and emphasized the importance of inclusivity and collaboration. Intentional information fabrication and gaining information through opponents' networks were deemed the most impactful, reflecting differing views on the efficacy and ethical consequences of competing strategies.

Wholesalers View

Wholesalers in Batangas prioritize compassion, professionalism, and honesty in negotiation to build strong relationships with distributors and secure preferred customer status. They believe in effective communication, humility, and respect for each other's needs. They seek preferred customer status by fostering positive connections, making communication easy, and demonstrating dependability in delivering orders and payments. They value meeting quotas, demonstrating respect, and remaining professional in all interactions with distributors.

Wholesalers are aware of the risks of competitive negotiation behaviors like deception, bluffing, and network manipulation. Honesty, transparency, and ethical business practices are emphasized to foster trust and sustain economic integrity. To attain preferred customer status, wholesalers focus on techniques that encourage collaboration and mutual support with distributors through integrative negotiation behaviors.

Respondents generally agreed that factors such as being aware of the counterpart's demands, seeking mutual satisfaction, maintaining healthy personal relationships, collaborating for positive results, and ensuring a free flow of information had little to no impact on positive working relationships. However, behaviors such as limiting gaps between parties, trusting other negotiators' perspectives, allowing participation in decision-making, and employing deceptive tactics were highly regarded for generating competitive advantages.

Similarities and differences between Distributors and Wholesalers View Theme

Table 3. Good working relationship

Negotiation Behaviors	Good working relations				
	Distributors'		Wholesaler'		Description*
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent	1.20	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network	1.40	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Gaining information about a party by paying its contacts	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs	4.60	to a very great extent.	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Seeking mutual satisfaction	3.80	to a great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Ensuring a positive and productive	5.00	to a very great extent.	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar

personal relationship					
Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties	5.00	to a very great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators	4.80	to a very great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Minimizing differences among the parties	4.70	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar
Trusting the position and information of other negotiators	4.40	to a great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process	4.60	to a very great extent	4.40	to a great extent	Similar

*Description is based on the interpretation comparison between distributors 'and wholesalers'

Good working relationship. Both distributors and wholesalers in Batangas have similar negotiation behaviors used to have good working relationships. Both of them emphasize the importance of connection-building, satisfaction, ethical conduct, and integrative negotiation behaviors in negotiations. They believe that trust, collaboration, and mutual satisfaction are crucial for securing preferred customer status and achieving long-term partnerships. Both parties improve business outcomes. They also emphasize the importance of fair and transparent processes, fostering a favorable negotiation climate. This alignment demonstrates a shared understanding of cooperative and mutually beneficial negotiation techniques.

Table 4. Working relationships that convey competitive advantage.

Negotiation Behaviors	Working relationships that convey competitive advantage.				
	Distributors'		Wholesaler'		Description*
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
Intentionally misrepresenting factual	1.20	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar

information to the opponent					
Gaining information about an opponent by using the opponent's network	1.40	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Gaining information about a party by paying its contacts	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to	1.00	to a very little or no extent	1.00	to a very little or no extent	Similar
Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs	4.60	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar
Seeking mutual satisfaction	3.80	to a great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship	5.00	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar
Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties	5.00	to a very great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Ensuring a free flow of information	4.80	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar

among negotiators					
Minimizing differences among the parties	4.70	to a very great extent	5.00	to a very great extent.	Similar
Trusting the position and information of other negotiators	4.50	to a very great extent	4.90	to a very great extent.	Similar
Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process	4.60	to a very great extent	4.50	to a very great extent.	Similar

*Description is based on the interpretation comparison between distributors 'and wholesalers'

Working relationships that convey competitive advantage. Both distributors and wholesalers in Batangas have similar negotiation behaviors used to have working relationships that convey competitive advantage. Both of them focus on excellent communication, relationship-building tactics, and ethical behavior in their negotiation practices. They appreciate the value of understanding customer needs, demonstrating product knowledge, and cultivating great relationships in order to increase wholesaler loyalty and attain preferred customer status. Despite differences in attitudes regarding competitive negotiation strategies, distributors consistently underline the importance of active listening, trust-building, and participatory decision-making in developing corporate partnerships and driving successful outcomes. There is agreement on the negative impact of unethical behaviors on relationships and preferred customer status, despite the fact that some negotiation techniques garnered mixed reviews.

Table 5. Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice

Negotiation Behaviors	Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice				Description*
	Distributors'		Wholesaler'		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
Intentionally misrepresenting factual information to the opponent	1.30	not at all	1.00	not at all	Similar
Gaining information about an opponent by using the	1.40	not at all	1.00	not at all	Similar

opponent's network					
Bluffing that it can get its goods somewhere else	1.00	not at all	1.00	not at all	Similar
Gaining information about a party by paying its contacts	1.00	not at all	1.00	not at all	Similar
Manipulating the other party by talking to people this party accounts to	1.00	not at all	1.00	not at all	Similar
Ensuring understanding of the counterpart's needs	6.40	great	6.90	very great	Similar
Seeking mutual satisfaction	5.20	considerable	5.20	considerable	Similar
Ensuring a positive and productive personal relationship	7.00	very great	6.90	very great	Similar
Cooperating to obtain positive results from the parties	7.00	very great	7.00	very great	Similar
Ensuring a free flow of information among negotiators	7.00	very great	6.90	very great	Similar
Minimizing differences among the parties	6.60	very great	6.80	very great	Similar

Trusting the position and information of other negotiators	6.20	great	6.40	great	Similar
Allowing participation of all parties in the decision-making process	6.50	very great	6.90	very great	Similar

*Description is based on the interpretation comparison between distributors 'and wholesalers'

Recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice. Both distributors and wholesalers in Batangas have similar negotiation behaviors used to have recognition of the buyer as a customer of choice. They place a premium on professionalism, and honesty in their negotiation behaviors in order to build great connections with distributors and secure preferred customer status. They prioritize good communication, humility, and dependability in their contacts, recognizing the importance of trust and prioritizing the well-being of distribution people. Wholesalers recognize the hazards associated with competitive negotiation behaviors and highlight the need for honesty, transparency, and ethical standards in building trust and maintaining business relationships. Furthermore, wholesalers prioritize integrative negotiation methods, such as active listening and collaboration, to better understand distributor demands and build trust, which influences their chances of reaching preferred customer status.

Both distributors and wholesalers in Batangas have similar negotiation behaviors and decision-making processes. They understand the value of connection-building, contentment, ethical behavior, and collaboration in achieving success and retaining preferred customer status. While there may be differences in opinions and attitudes toward specific negotiation tactics, the overall purpose remains the same: to establish excellent working relationships, increase mutual satisfaction, and facilitate long-term partnerships that benefit both parties.

Conclusions

Distributors View

Batangas distributors prioritize communication skills, account knowledge, timeliness, and relationship-building strategies in customer negotiations. They value preferred customer status based on factors like character, payment regularity, and loyalty. Some use deception tactics, such as bluffing and manipulation, to increase sales, raising ethical concerns. Active listening and understanding demands are critical for establishing trust and strengthening corporate partnerships. Inclusive decision-making methods are appreciated for considering multiple perspectives and generating mutually beneficial

outcomes. Minimizing disagreements and establishing trust are essential components of effective negotiations.

Respondents ranked cooperation, open communication, and trusting the stance of other negotiators as bad. They supported participation in decision-making and emphasized the importance of inclusivity and collaboration. Intentional information fabrication and gaining information through opponents' networks were deemed the most impactful, reflecting differing views on the efficacy and ethical consequences of competing strategies.

Wholesalers View

Wholesalers in Batangas prioritize compassion, professionalism, and honesty in negotiation to build strong relationships with distributors and secure preferred customer status. They believe in effective communication, humility, and respect for each other's needs. They seek preferred customer status by fostering positive connections, making communication easy, and demonstrating respect, and remaining professional in all interactions with distributors.

Wholesalers prioritize honesty, transparency, and ethical business practices to maintain trust and economic integrity. They focus on integrative negotiation behaviors to gain preferred customer status. Factors like understanding counterparts' demands, satisfaction, and personal relationships have minimal impact on positive working relationships. However, limiting gaps, trusting perspectives, and employing deceptive tactics generate competitive advantages.

Both distributors and wholesalers in Batangas have similar negotiation behaviors and decision-making processes. They understand the value of connection-building, contentment, ethical behavior, and collaboration in achieving success and retaining preferred customer status. While there may be differences in opinions and attitudes toward specific negotiation tactics, the overall purpose remains the same: to establish excellent working relationships, increase mutual satisfaction, and facilitate long-term partnerships that benefit both parties.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from distributors and wholesalers in Batangas, numerous recommendations may be given for wholesalers to follow in order to achieve customer-preferred status:

1. **Prioritize Communication Excellence:** Wholesalers may invest in improving their communication skills, such as active listening and clear concept expression. Regular and transparent contact with distributors builds trust and displays a desire to maintain great relationships.
2. **Emphasize Relationship Building:** Wholesalers may prioritize developing true, long-term relationships with distributors founded on trust, respect, and mutual understanding. This means dedicating time and effort to getting to know distributors personally,

understanding their needs, and proactively addressing any complaints or challenges that may occur.

3. **Demonstrate Ethical Behavior:** Wholesalers are expected to maintain high ethical standards throughout their relationships with distributors. This comprises honesty, transparency, and integrity in the negotiation process, as well as a dedication to fair and ethical commercial practices. Avoiding dishonest techniques and focusing on ethical behavior fosters trust and credibility with distributors, increasing the likelihood of earning preferred customer status.

4. **Encourage collaboration and inclusivity:** Wholesalers may actively involve distributors in decision-making processes and solicit their feedback on critical business choices. Collaborative decision-making fosters a sense of ownership and partnership, resulting in increased distributor satisfaction and loyalty. Furthermore, wholesalers should be receptive to comments and suggestions from distributors, exhibiting a desire to adapt and collaborate for mutual gain.

5. **Active Listening:** To excel in handling distributor needs, it is crucial to exhibit active listening skills and pay close attention to their issues and feedback. By doing so, we can effectively understand their concerns and provide satisfactory solutions to ensure their utmost satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers have an ethical obligation to conduct research ethically, prioritizing knowledge while respecting the rights and well-being of participants and society. Balancing potential benefits with potential costs is crucial, and researchers must ensure voluntary participation, inform respondents of the right to withdraw, and provide clarity on the study's purpose and procedures. Participants should have the right to ask questions, access results, and maintain privacy and confidentiality.

Researchers should outline individual benefits, secure agreement through signatures, obtain permission for site access, commit to unbiased language, and avoid fraudulent practices. Proactive consideration of the study's impact and prevention of result misuse are essential. Acting ethically requires a balance between advancing knowledge and noninterference in others' lives, with absolute rights for participants or researchers posing challenges. Legal and ethical prohibitions include avoiding unnecessary harm, securing voluntary consent, and respecting participants. Participants should be informed about the study's purpose, procedures, duration, associated risks, confidentiality measures, researcher identification, and avenues for information or questions.

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